

PACE: Predictive Adjusted Capped Estimator for Quarterly Business Forecasting

by Vinodhkumar Gunasekaran

Abstract PACE introduces the first automated capped hybrid growth model for quarterly forecasting in business and public-sector planning. It averages year-over-year, rolling quarter-over-quarter, and prior-quarter growth rates, applies asymmetric volatility caps, incorporates seasonal factors, and updates history online. On a 24,000-series M4-style benchmark, PACE achieves 22% lower sMAPE than `forecast`'s `auto.arima()` and 34% lower error than `prophet`, with zero explosive forecasts and no parameter tuning. The algorithm formalizes a common financial-planning heuristic into a reproducible R package.

1 Introduction

Quarterly business forecasting faces regime shifts, budget scrutiny, and the risk of unrealistic growth projections. Spreadsheet-style growth caps are common in FP&A practice. Automated methods such as `auto.arima()` (Hyndman and Khandakar, 2008) and `prophet()` (Taylor and Letham, 2024) can spike under shocks without guardrails.

PACE formalizes this intuition: it averages interpretable growth signals and enforces fixed asymmetric caps, producing stable forecasts without tuning.

2 Contribution to the R Ecosystem

PACE contributes a practical, interpretable quarterly forecaster to the R ecosystem. While `forecast` and `prophet` provide powerful automated and machine-learning methods, they may generate extreme trajectories without manual constraints. PACE fills this gap by formalizing business planning heuristics into a deterministic, tuning-free algorithm that runs in milliseconds and avoids explosive paths, making it well-suited for FP&A, macroeconomic planning, and retail demand workflows.

3 Methodology

Let y_t be the latest observed value. Forecast one period ahead:

$$\hat{y}_{t+1} = y_t(1 + g_t)s_{q(t+1)}.$$

Growth signal:

$$g_t = \frac{1}{3}[\text{cap}(YoY_t) + \text{cap}(\overline{QoQ}_{t-3:t}) + \text{cap}(\text{PriorQoQ}_t)].$$

Asymmetric capping:

$$\text{cap}(x) = \min(\max(x, -0.25), 0.50).$$

Seasonal factor:

$$s_q = \frac{\bar{y}_q}{\frac{1}{4} \sum_{r=1}^4 \bar{y}_r}.$$

Online update:

$$y_{t+1} \leftarrow \hat{y}_{t+1}.$$

Method	sMAPE	Explosive (> 200%)
PACE	9.41	0
auto.arima	12.08	1204
ETS	11.49	892
Prophet	14.27	2108
TBATS	12.31	678
Theta	11.88	512

Table 1: M4-style quarterly benchmark (24,000 series).

4 Benchmark

5 Example

```
library(PACE)
apple <- data.frame(
  Time=seq(as.Date("2020-01-01"), by="quarter", length.out=16),
  Value=c(58.3, 59.7, 64.7, 81.4, 83.0, 94.8, 81.8, 83.4,
          89.5, 123.9, 117.2, 119.6, 94.3, 97.3, 90.8, 119.6))
fc <- pace_forecast_seasonal(apple, periods=4)
plot_pace(fc, apple)
```

6 Simulation

We simulate 500 quarterly random-walk series with seasonal patterns and shocks; **PACE** yields mean sMAPE 8.7 vs 11.3 for `auto.arima()`, with no unstable paths. Code is provided in ‘benchmarks.R’.

7 Reproducibility

All data and scripts are on GitHub: <https://github.com/vinoalles/PACE>

A reproducible script ‘benchmarks.R’ accompanies the submission.

8 Conclusion

PACE provides stable, interpretable quarterly forecasts without tuning. Future work includes monthly extension and hierarchical reconciliation.

Bibliography

R. Hyndman and Y. Khandakar. Automatic time series forecasting: the forecast package for r. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 27(3):1–22, 2008. [p1]

S. J. Taylor and B. Letham. *prophet: Automatic Forecasting Procedure*, 2024. URL <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=prophet>. [p1]

Vinodhkumar Gunasekaran
 Circana (formerly IRI)
 Chicago, USA
 ORCID: 0000-0002-0817-0923
vinoalles@gmail.com